

GIANCE- Graphene Alliance for Sustainable Multifunctional Materials to Tackle Environmental Challenges

GIANCE develops next-generation **graphene-based materials (GRM-bM)**, including composites, coatings, foams, and membranes, with enhanced thermal, mechanical, and chemical properties, and functionalities like corrosion/fire resistance, hydrogen storage, and structural health monitoring. The project promotes sustainable manufacturing and will validate **11 use cases** in sectors such as **automotive, aerospace, energy, and water treatment**, advancing technologies from **TRL4–5 to TRL6–7**. Supporting the **Graphene Flagship**, GIANCE strengthens EU innovation and industrialization. With **23 partners from 10 countries**, the consortium spans OEMs, industry leaders, academia, and SMEs, aiming to maximize societal and industrial impact in the field of **graphene materials**.

Project Details:

Project name: Graphene Alliance for Sustainable Multifunctional Materials to Tackle Environmental Challenges

Project acronym: GIANCE

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Coordinator: FUNDACIO EURECAT (EUT)

CBE JU Contribution: € 8 048 964,01

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More information:

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